

FAIR4RS

Research Software Definition workshop

Collaborative notes - 23 February 2021 - First meeting

10:00 CEST

Useful links

[RDA group page](#),

[GitHub repository](#)

[Gitter chat](#)

[Subgroup3 document \(collection of quotes, collection of example\)](#)

Agenda

00:00	Welcome & introductions
00:05	The concept of an "inclusive" vs. "exclusive" definition
00:35	Software examples to complete report's case study
01:10	The "chicken or the egg dilemma" of software in a scholarly infrastructure
01:25	Conclusion and next steps (proceeding with the output)

Participants in 1st meeting

- **Add your name, institution, job title, country, member, if want to participate actively in the output production**

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<https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/fair-4-research-software-fair4rs-wg>

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If you have provided this information in the past just add your name and ORCID

Name + ORCID	Institution/affiliation	Job title	Country	I want to participate actively in the output production of Research Software Definition
Morane Gruenpeter	Inria, Software Heritage	Software engineer and metadata specialist	France	Yes
Matthias Liffers	Australian Research Data Commons	Research Software Skills Specialist	Australia	
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Esther Plomp	Dutch technology university	Data steward	Netherlands	
Leyla	ZBMED		Germany	

Notes from 1st meeting

1.1 The concept of an "inclusive" vs. "exclusive" definition

You can add aspects to the table or comment on the existing aspects.

Inclusive approach	Exclusive approach
Software that can be related to research	Software that is a product/result of research
Software products on which research depends	Software that came from a research team in a research institution
Software used for data (or models and methods?)	Software that is by itself a scientific/academic discovery
Collecting data, Preparing data, Sharing data,	Analyzing data
Both industrial/commercial and academic research may use/produce software to solve problems to benefit society.	Software that could be or was accepted to an academic journal (JOSS, IPOL, eLife)
Software dependency stack	Software that was badged by a scholarly institution
	Software that was reviewed in an academic evaluation
Software that captures research related processes in some way	Software that is innovative and is a major contribution to science or academia
	Software needed to reproduce science
Cloud based services which provide access to data	The software needed by research but not met by the commercial sector
Software developed in industrial or military research	Software that can be made FAIR

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Hinsen's software stack:

- (1) "...infrastructure created specifically for scientific computing, but not any particular domain."
- (2) "...domain specific research software. These are tools and libraries that implement models and methods which are developed and used by communities ranging in size from a single research lab to thousands of researchers"
- (3) "...software written by scientists for a specific research project...scripts, notebooks, and workflows, but also special-purpose libraries and utilities."

And then the paper also excludes layers that underpin all of this:

- (4) "Infrastructure software that is not specific to scientific computing. ... compilers and interpreters, libraries for data management, but also higher level tools such as text editors and Web browsers. ... obtain[ed] from the wider non-scientific software market"
- (5) operating system
- (6) Hardware"

Name	In your opinion, which approach is better for a Research Software definition?	Where is the limit for software that should be FAIR? (you can choose a layer from Hinsen's software stack or describe a limit)
Morane	I'm leaning towards the exclusive approach for different reasons, first a pragmatic reason - having all software products FAIR is not realistic. Also, by choosing the exclusive approach we focus software which has an academic impact as a research discovery. It is like choosing to focus on diamonds, instead of requiring all stones to be FAIR. At the moment even the diamonds are not acknowledged in academia.	Hinsen's layers are a good example of required software for reproducibility, but it is impossible to say that layer 1 is research discovery and/ or a major contribution for science. I personally think that the limit should be on software that is identified by its creators as an academic discovery and that with this identification, the creators decide to add citation information and/or publish the software in an academic venue (which might be a journal, a research catalog/registry or an academic deposit - HAL, Zenodo or an Institutional Repository)
LJ	I would go for a balanced approach , based on community consensus, maybe around examples and exclusion points. Now, an exclusion point does	All of those excluded by Hinsen's seem reasonable to me (4, 5, 6) but, if a compiler is born as a research software and authors want to keep it

	not mean that FAIR cannot be applied but we did not take that case into account in FAIR4RS. It should be flexible and be allowed to evolve as well.	labeled as such and still take care of being compatible with FAIR4RS, well, why not keep it?
TH	I'm leaning towards a broad but exclusive approach. It's got to have boundaries .	I like the Hinsen approach but I find the boundary between scientific and non scientific software infrastructure a bit blurry . I've been leaning toward thinking of the second layer as novel domain or discipline specific software , and the third layer as generally accepted discipline, domain or multi-domain software often implemented more than once. For the boundary, I've been fairly accepting of potentially commercial solutions, if we include them, they may well not be interested in FAIR anyway and not affected by policy directed at the research sector.
CM	I think it depends on the objective. For example, if your objective is to be able to reproduce a result, you should capture all software which is necessary for reproducing that result. Even further, if to reproduce that result you require specific hardware, then details of such hardware should be preserved (e.g. specific type of GPU)	
AlexS	I'd prefer two dedicated definitions. An inclusive one to get recognition for everything that supports research. And an exclusive definition as a different view and maybe usable for FAIR. Maybe two definitions can be useful in more contexts or situations.	Infrastructure can now be defined by software, see e.g. Docker and its networking etc.
ML	I would prefer an inclusive approach, but to be honest that's my approach to life. An exclusive approach can be tarnished by using the wrong words, such as limiting "research" to "science".	The stack is tricky - for software to be FAIR, wouldn't its dependencies also need to be FAIR to some degree?
EPP	I'm a bit torn: I hope that we can be	1 and 3 seem particularly helpful. 3 if

	<p>inclusive in the definition but at the same time this will not provide more clarity/boundaries in terms of what should be made FAIR. I think if you would like to set boundaries it would be logical to connect it to other scientific outputs such as data/publications? But then it should be clear that it is a definition for Research Software that is very much focused on a snapshot endresult and not covering the entire process.</p>	<p>you want to limit the scope further. Not sure if I agree about 4 being excluded for a general research software definition but for FAIR, sure.</p>
PH	<p>Depends on what you want to do with this in the end, if it should relate to some kind of practical implementation, I think it needs to be exclusive somehow just for pragmatic reasons</p>	<p>2 and 3 - 1 and 4-6 maybe go more into the area of service/infrastructure and other FAIR assessments can be applied then?</p>
LS	<p>Start with an exclusive approach and if necessary extend it to an inclusive approach. Researchers should see how far they can go.</p>	<p>1, 2, 3 should be transparent about how FAIR they are.</p>

1.2 Software examples to complete report's case study

Ipol example

The screenshot shows the IPOL Journal website interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with links for HOME, ABOUT, ARTICLES, PREPRINTS, WORKSHOPS, NEWS, and SEARCH. The main title of the article is "An Analysis and Implementation of the Shape Preserving Local Histogram Modification Algorithm" by Jose-Luis Lisani. Below the title, there are tabs for "article", "demo", and "archive". A green banner indicates the publication date as 2018-12-07 and provides a BibTeX reference. The abstract describes the implementation of an algorithm for local contrast enhancement. A "Download" section offers full text manuscripts in PDF (low-res and standard) and source code in TAR/GZ. A "Preview" section shows a low-resolution PDF thumbnail with a Software Heritage ID tooltip. The tooltip contains the following text: "Software Heritage ID (https://www.softwareheritage.org): /swh:1:dir:d85591aeefa2c1c58142e34683fd1923b19c895; origin=https://doi.org/10.5201/ipol.2018.236; visit=swh:1:snp:e0674ffb865529b95511808d1ee7ba5d72346009; anchor=swh:1:rev:fad7a0486bb7a7cfdbb1c28e28a64f2d3f5e0df9; path=-". The article title and author information are also visible in the preview area.

Figure 1: View of a publication on the IPOL Journal platform

Jose-Luis Lisani, *An Analysis and Implementation of the Shape Preserving Local Histogram Modification Algorithm*, *Image Processing On Line*, 8 (2018), pp. 408–434. <https://doi.org/10.5201/ipol.2018.236>

Question	IPOL published implementation answers	Was this question helpful to determine if the software is RS
Is the software created with a research or commercial purpose?	[MG] academic [LJ] research (which does not mean that	[LJ] Looks at first sight as typical research sw so maybe not

	<p>is cannot used as commercial) [LS] that is not clear, things can start as research with an implicit purpose to use it commercially [TH] probably research, but could be commercial too? [ML] Unclear</p>	<p>[TH] false dichotomy... can be both research and commercial. Not helpful [AS] not helpful as research happens everywhere (industry, military, academy) [LS] Not helpful. It raises a lot of questions. [CM]: I think it helps a to understand the context a bit.</p> <p>[EPP]: Not helpful in my opinion, raises more questions than providing clarity</p>
<p>Is the software primarily used for purposes outside of research?</p>	<p>[LJ] Cannot tell but the (initial) purpose of the authors seem to be research [AS] sounds like improvement of a tool but the paper lacks a research motivation. But we see some grants. [Th] not enough info [ML] Not enough information</p>	<p>[AS] question only partly helpful as I could not tell from the paper where it was or should be used. [EPP]: Not helpful in my opinion, raises more questions than providing clarity [TH] not helpful. It may start as research-bound, and then become applicable outside research</p>
<p>Is the software/code needed for reproducing data analysis/results? deliver research results?</p>	<p>[LJ] It is for images, images are data so, I am guessing yes [ML] The software is needed for reproducing the analysis of itself</p>	<p>[TH] seems very narrow. Although I might have this requirement (reproduction of results) outside a research context too. [LJ] Not necessarily, Python is used to reproduce results, I would not categorized it as RS (nowadays)</p>
<p>Is there a paper about the software?</p>	<p>[MG] yes [ML] yes [AS] yes and more around it [LJ] Yes</p>	<p>[AS] it's a software-related academic text publication and this would be helpful for a definition work [LJ] A paper is a good way to guess yes, it is RS [TH] seems too narrow [CM]: Yes, but software without a paper could also be RS</p>
<p>Is there a research result that is dependent on this software?</p>	<p>[MG] unknown [LJ] I imagine yes, at least a contrast between the two implementations</p>	<p>[AS] hardly helpful as we do not yet know what to in/exclude from the software stack. [LJ] Lot of research results depend on Python [TH] I'm just not sure what is meant by "dependent" here</p>
<p>Could the software be replaced with other software without affecting the research results?</p>	<p>[MG] unknown (needs more investigation) [TH] yes</p>	<p>[AS] hardly helpful because cluster algorithms are supposed to be general purpose (network research)</p>

	<p>[LJ] It looks like yes because is an implementation [ML] No, because the results of the research are about the software itself</p>	<p>tools. "In an exclusive approach, an implementation in a different language is not RS" (MG) [LJ] Do not see how it helps [TH] This seems like a more useful criterion for determining the uniqueness of a tool. But otherwise unhelpful for determining if RS</p>
<p>Was the software developed by a researcher? Or in an academic context?</p>	<p>[PH] corresponding author is at a university [ML] Yes [AS] we see grants but do not know if they are military or academic [LS] Yes, you can look it up in the article. [LJ] Looks like yes</p>	<p>[PH] somehow useful, don't think it should be the only criterion taking into account [LS] Helpful, it makes clear that the software was developed in an academic context. [LJ] Yes, looks like a typical example [TH] helpful, except clarify "researcher", and "academic context" seems overly restrictive [EPP] Not helpful: what about research institutes that are not necessarily part of an academic institute and industry research teams?</p>
<p>Was the software evaluated or reviewed as part of a research process? (ACM badge, peer review, research institution committee, etc.)</p>	<p>[ML] unknown - would need to look up IPOL's peer review process [LJ] No idea, reviewing the paper is not the same as reviewing the sw</p>	<p>[TH] doesn't seem useful, unless you want to define research software exclusively as a scholarly output [LJ] Not much, not sure how sw reviewing is required/done for research... it is important, yes, but detailed review can take too long and reviewers are commonly not paid for it so not sure how much time would be dedicated to go to all the details. I would say metadata (e.g., the one needed for FAIR) would be easier to "review"</p>
<p>Would a researcher be expected to cite this software?</p>	<p>[PH] recommendation is to cite the associated paper [AS] yes, because common in research [LJ] Looks like yes [TH]... they could cite the paper or the software... so strictly speaking no</p>	<p>[PH] software citation hasn't been picked up widely, so not sure if that is a useful criterion [EPP] Citation could be a result of software being FAIR, so I think this question is helpful. [LJ] Yes [AS] Due to common practice to document what your research is based on, a citation (expectation/recommendation) may be used as an indicator for something being a research result (but we still have</p>

SciPy example

swMATH Search Advanced search Browse

SciPy

SciPy (pronounced "Sigh Pie") is open-source software for mathematics, science, and engineering. It is also the name of a very popular conference on scientific programming with Python. The SciPy library depends on NumPy, which provides convenient and fast N-dimensional array manipulation. The SciPy library is built to work with NumPy arrays, and provides many user-friendly and efficient numerical routines such as routines for numerical integration and optimization. Together, they run on all popular operating systems, are quick to install, and are free of charge. NumPy and SciPy are easy to use, but powerful enough to be depended upon by some of the world's leading scientists and engineers. If you need to manipulate numbers on a computer and display or publish the results, give SciPy a try!

Keywords for this software

Python package Python parameter estimation
 Journal of Open Research Software
 Machine Learning
 arXiv publication JOSS publication
 Astrophysics
 Journal of Open Research Software
 arXiv astro-ph.IM
 arXiv stat.ML
 JOSS
 classification arXiv
 Journal of Open Source Software
 arXiv cs.LG simulation
 machine learning convergence
 Software arXiv quant-ph
 Python Quantum Physics

References in zbMATH (referenced in 492 articles)

Showing results 1 to 20 of 492. Sorted by year (citations) 20

1 2 3 ... 23 24 25 next

1. Chaudhry, Jehanzeb H.; Collins, J. B.: 'textitAposteriori error estimation for the spectral deferred correction method (2021)
2. Karban, Pavel; Pánek, David; Orosz, Tamás; Petrášová, Iveta; Doležel, Ivo: FEM based robust design optimization with Agros and Ártap (2021)
3. Aguirre-Mesa, Andres M.; Garcia, Manuel J.; Millwater, Harry: MultIZ: a library for computation of high-order derivatives using multicomplex or multidual numbers (2020)
4. Alain Jungo, Olivier Scheidegger, Mauricio Reyes, Fabian Balsiger: pymia: A Python package for data handling and evaluation in deep learning-based medical image analysis (2020) arXiv
5. Allen, Henry R.; Ptashnyk, Mariya: Mathematical modelling of auxin transport in plant tissues: flux meets signalling and growth (2020)
6. Andò, Alessia; Breda, Dimitri; Scardabel, Francesca: Numerical continuation and delay equations: a novel approach for complex models of structured populations (2020)
7. Andrew R. McCluskey, Tim Snow: uravu: Making Bayesian modelling easy(er) (2020) not zbMATH
8. Andrieux, Stephane; Baranger, Thouraya N.: Nonlinear Cauchy problem and identification in contact mechanics: a solving method based on Bregman-gap (2020)
9. Archis S. Joglekar, Matthew C. Levy: ViaPy: A Python package for Eulerian Vlasov-Poisson-Fokker-Planck

Article statistics & filter:

Search for articles

MSC classification / top

- Top MSC classes
- 35 Partial differential...
- 65 Numerical analysis
- 68 Computer science
- 76 Fluid mechanics
- 92 Applications of...
- Other MSC classes

Publication year

- 2010 - today
- 2005 - 2009
- 2000 - 2004
- before 2000

Chart: cumulative / absolute

Figure 2: SciPY entry in swMATH registry which shows an metadata about SciPy and the list of citations where SciPy was cited (492 articles) accessed on February 22, 2021 on <https://swmath.org/software/6293>

Question	swMath entry- SciPy answers	Was this question helpful to determine if the software is RS
Is the software created with a research or commercial purpose?	[AS] obviously from the name	
Is the software primarily used for purposes outside of research?		

Is the software/code needed for reproducing data analysis/results? deliver research results?		
Is there a paper about the software ?		
Is there a research result that is dependent on this software?		
Could the software be replaced with other software without affecting the research results?		
Was the software developed by a researcher ? Or in an academic context ?		
Was the software evaluated or reviewed as part of a research process? (ACM badge, peer review, research institution committee, etc.)		
Would a researcher be expected to cite this software?		

Excel example

Weissgerber TL, Milic NM, Winham SJ, Garovic VD. Beyond bar and line graphs: time for a new data presentation paradigm. PLoS Biol. 2015 Apr 22;13(4):e1002128.
<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.1002128>

Question	swMath entry-SciPy answers	Was this question helpful to determine if the software is RS
Is the software created with a research or commercial purpose?		
Is the software primarily used for purposes outside of research?		
Is the software/code needed for reproducing data analysis/results? deliver research results?		
Is there a paper about the software?		

Is there a research result that is dependent on this software?		
Could the software be replaced with other software without affecting the research results?		
Was the software developed by a researcher ? Or in an academic context ?		
Was the software evaluated or reviewed as part of a research process? (ACM badge, peer review, research institution committee, etc.)		
Would a researcher be expected to cite this software?		

Scala example

An Overview of the Scala Programming Language

Second Edition

Martin Odersky, Philippe Altherr, Vincent Cremet, Iulian Dragos
 Gilles Dubochet, Burak Emir, Sean McDirmid, Stéphane Micheloud,
 Nikolay Mihaylov, Michel Schinz, Erik Stenman, Lex Spoon, Matthias Zenger

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Technical Report LAMP-REPORT-2006-091

Abstract

Scala fuses object-oriented and functional programming in a statically typed programming language. It is aimed at the construction of components and component systems. This paper gives an overview of the Scala language for readers who are familiar with programming methods and programming language design.

1 Introduction

True component systems have been an elusive goal of the software industry. Ideally, software should be assembled

language for component software needs to be scalable in the sense that the same concepts can describe small as well as large parts. Therefore, we concentrate on mechanisms for abstraction, composition, and decomposition rather than adding a large set of primitives which might be useful for components at some level of scale, but not at other levels. Second, we postulate that scalable support for components can be provided by a programming language which unifies and generalizes object-oriented and functional programming. For statically typed languages, of which Scala is an instance, these two paradigms were up to now largely separate.

To validate our hypotheses, Scala needs to be applied to the design of component- and component systems. (Odersky et al., 2004)

Functional Programming + Object-oriented Programming = Scala

Figure 4: A combined figure from the first page of the first Scala publication (cited 782 times accessed on google scholar on February 22, 2021) and a diagram explaining scala Odersky, M., Altherr, P., Cremet, V., Emir, B., Maneth, S., Micheloud, S., ... & Zenger, M. (2004). An overview of the Scala programming language. Technical Report IC/2004/64

Question	What is the `it` here?	Was this question helpful to determine if the software is RS
Is the software created with a research or commercial purpose ?	<p>[ML] A programming language isn't software, in the same way that the English language is not a publication</p> <p>[LS] The it seems to be the programming language. It had it credits. Others can now create research software with it.</p> <p>[LJ] At that point in time (2008) maybe research but even if commercial, it still can be RS</p>	<p>[AS] hardly helpful as the language was a research result a long time ago and is definitely used in industry today.</p> <p>[LJ] Not sure</p>
Is the software primarily used for purposes outside of research?	<p>[LJ] Not aware of stats when the article was published or now</p>	<p>[AS] over the years the use cases may have changed from purely academic to industry now.</p> <p>[LJ] Not sure</p>
Is the software/code needed for reproducing data analysis/results? deliver research results?	<p>[LJ] Yes</p>	<p>[LJ] Yes</p>
Is there a paper about the software ?	<p>[LJ] Yes</p>	<p>[AS] Helpful if we agree that a peer-reviewed paper is a valid evaluation proxy for a piece of software.</p> <p>[LJ] Yes, I would say that gives the idea that, at least at some point in time, research was the aim... so, maybe programming languages can be RS</p>
Is there a research result that is dependent on this software?	<p>[TH] maybe not, assuming you mean the result question that began the work, not things written in scala</p> <p>[LJ] Yes, any RS written in Scala</p>	<p>[AS] That is hard to tell because it's a programming language inherently created to build tools, so the same algorithm in a different language may solve the same problem. So, in case of programming language, this question is not helpful.</p> <p>[LJ] Not sure</p>

<p>Could the software be replaced with other software without affecting the research results?</p>	<p>[LJ] Hard to say, I guess yes, I guess other programming language can have similar features</p>	<p>[LJ] Not sure</p>
<p>Was the software developed by a researcher? Or in an academic context?</p>	<p>[th] originally yes, and then... [LJ] Looks like at that point, yes [LS] yes</p>	<p>[AS] not helpful as some algorithms used in network research have been developed by the military or by military funding (Example Ward Clustering). Should we consider that "academic"?</p>
<p>Was the software evaluated or reviewed as part of a research process? (ACM badge, peer review, research institution committee, etc.)</p>	<p>[th] no? Looks like the paper was reviewed [LS] the programming language was evaluated.</p>	<p>[PH] not sure - it seems to be widely used, so that is an evaluation by the wide public maybe? [LS] reviewed by academic peers can be a useful question.</p>
<p>Would a researcher be expected to cite this software?</p>	<p>[TH] no [LJ] Yes, at that time at least</p>	<p>[LJ] Yes (at that time) it would give clues of this to be an RS</p>

1.3 The "chicken or the egg dilemma" of software in a scholarly infrastructure

1. Software in a scholarly infrastructure is Research Software
2. Research Software should be registered and deposited in a scholarly infrastructure

We might want to identify RS by its location and dissemination (in or by a scholarly infrastructure) but at the same time we want to tell software creators to use the scholarly infrastructures for their RS.

“Software that researchers in any discipline may feel the need to have *scholarly infrastructure support for*, no matter if it is considered a *tool*, a *result* or an *object of study*”

European Commission. Directorate General for Research and Innovation. (2020). Scholarly infrastructures for research software: report from the EOSC Executive Board Working Group (WG) Architecture Task Force (TF) SIRS. Publications Office. <https://doi.org/10.2777/28598>

Name	Should we use the software dissemination as a way to identify RS? Why? Why not?	Comments on answer
Morane		
Matthias	Absolutely not. It's far too prescriptive. You might as well say that research isn't research unless it results in an article published in an Elsevier journal.	[AS] Fully agreed. But, we have a situation where research that is not published in a journal indexed by WoS/Scopus may not be seen or be visible or evaluated as research. Just adding the evaluative angle here.
Alexander	No. Software is “published” on Github, local GitLabs, project websites, with or without PID, or maybe must be in a repository for journal article review. We cannot require/limit researchers to do a particular way, we have not yet implemented enough incentives for them to do so.	
Esther	<p>What is a scholarly infrastructure? Would Figshare/GitHub count as a scholarly infrastructure? Are journals scholarly infrastructure?</p> <p>Not sure if this is helpful for FAIR research software? As long as it is following the principles it shouldn't really matter if it is generated or deposited in a scholarly infrastructure? What about industrial infrastructures, volunteer efforts?</p>	[AS] Figshare/GitHub are commercially owned and block some researchers from accessing them. At the same time, most journals are commercially owned and not open.

Laurents	It could be a recommendation to publish it in a trusted repository.	
LJ	Not to identify it or for the definition. However, I can imagine FAIR4RS will encourage releases to be deposited/archived in a specialized registry or so (findability, PID characteristics).	
TH	No. Too prescriptive. What about software that is not openly available? And also, is it not research software before it is published, and only after?	[AS] Second the 2nd point because research software already solves a problem <u>before</u> it's being disseminated/published. It may even be reviewed by colleagues/peers.

1.4 Bonus question: who is expected to apply FAIR?

- a. The researcher / software creator
- b. The research institution / software authority (copyright holder)
- c. The infrastructures holding the software (repositories, registries, publishers, aggregators)
- d. Other

Name	Who is expected to apply FAIR?	why?
Matthias	Researcher/software creator	They are most familiar with it and have most control over how it is created. However, institutions/infrastructure/funders should make it easy for researchers/software creators to adhere to the FAIR principles.
Alexander	The funders (and a,b,c)	They can require FAIR principles for new research results, see for example

		Horizon2020 requirements.
Esther	All	The researcher/creator is responsible for making the software FAIR, but it is also the institution's responsibility to enable the researcher to do that as they generally hold the copyright. It is then also the infrastructure's responsibility to ensure that there are guidelines for archiving of the software and that the facilities are in place to ensure access and preservation.
Laurents	All	It is a collective action.
TH	All	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The creator knows what they did... they provide the detailed metadata - The owner has some responsibilities or obligations to ensure that the software is preserved - The infrastructure defines the bounds of what is captured against the software and the functionality for accessing/discovering it
LJ	If applying FAIR here means make sure that the RS is FAIR by adding to it all the FAIR required elements, the software developer/creator... hard for a third party to add all of it but it would be great if someone else is responsible, would not it? FAIR brings more work and researchers are already complaining about it but right now I do not see how third parties can take care of it. However, how to encourage, make use, facilitate FAIRness is everybody's work. So, e.g., infrastructures supporting FAIR go beyond the limits of the RS creator.	